

ON THE HEAT POLYMERISATION OF CASTOR OIL

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Castor oil polymerises at a fairly low temperature. It is observed that the increase in molecular weight is nearly 2 to 3 times its original value when the oil is heated for 4 hours at 100°. The oil is partly dehydrated and the Diene value increases within the range investigated.

The viscosity and specific gravity increase fairly proportionately with the increase in molecular weight. The process of polymerisation does not take place by simple doubling of molecules but is rather irregular as is evidenced by the increase in molecular weight which does not take place in simple multiples of the original oil.

Goswami and Saha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 1116) have shown that when boiled oil is prepared from linseed oil in presence of catalysts the olein and linolein of linseed oil at first form hydroxy compounds, which subsequently yield unsaturated compounds by elimination of water and finally give compounds having double bonds in conjugated positions.

The ricinoleic acid glyceride in castor oil on the other hand will directly lose a water molecule to form such compounds

by re-arrangement $\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{COO}-$

Synthetic drying oils with properties approaching to those of Tung oil have been prepared by abstracting a molecule of water from the castor oil molecule (Good, *Chem. Eng. News*, 1944, 18, 21) when, as indicated above, compounds having the molecular characteristics of Tung oil *i.e.* compounds containing double bonds in conjugated positions, are produced.

Now, once the conjugated system is introduced in the molecule it may be expected that it would take the course of typical butadiene polymerisation as follows :

The present paper is an attempt to study the course of polymerisation of castor oil when this oil is heated to moderately low temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The castor oil used was cold pressed in the laboratory, filtered and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Three sets of experiments were carried out at three different temperatures varying the duration of heating in each case. The temperatures inves-

tigated were 50°, 75° and 100° and in every case the oil was heated for 1, 2, 3 and 4 hours respectively.

The prepared samples were then examined under the following heads : specific gravity, refractive index, viscosity, iodine value, Diene value, acetyl value and molecular weight.

The refractive index was observed at 40° with a Butyro-Abbe refractometer. The viscosity of the samples was measured in a Redwood viscosimeter and results are expressed both in Redwood and Absolute units.

The Diene value or the maleic anhydride number, which is a measure of conjugated linkages in the system, was determined by the method of Kaufmann as modified by Baltes and Buter (*Ber.*, 1937, 70B, 903).

The molecular weight which indicates the state of polymerisation was found by the Beckmann's freezing point depression method in a benzene solution of the oil.

The results are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Oil heated for	Original oil.	Refractive index			Original oil.	Iodine value after heating at		
		50°.	75°.	100°.		50°.	75°.	100°.
0 hrs.	89.8	—	—	—	89.8	—	—	—
1		70.2	70.55	71.36		89.9	85.55	87.3
2		70.5	70.95	71.6		85.3	86.2	87.9
3		70.7	71.1	72		85.7	86.5	88.73
4		70.95	71.35	72.45		86.2	87.2	89.75

TABLE II

Condition.	Acetyl value.	Diene value.	Iodine value.
1. Original oil	145	2.95	89.8
2. Oil heated for 4 hrs. at 50°	136.8	6.4	86.2
3. " " at 70°	128.2	11.91	87.2
4. " " at 100°	117.8	28.2	89.75

The decrease in acetyl value accompanied by a simultaneous increase in iodine value and Diene value established the validity of our assumption, namely on heat treatment water molecules are eliminated at the expense of OH groups in ricinoleic acid glycerides with simultaneous increase in unsaturation.

It is also observed by plotting the relationship between (a) I.V. and refractive index (Fig. 1), (b) I.V. and acetyl value, and (c) iodine value and Diene values (Fig. 2) that (i) the variation of refractive index with iodine value is a linear one; (ii) the Diene value increases as the iodine value of the sample increases and (iii) the acetyl value does not increase proportionately with the increase in iodine value. The break in this curve might be explained thus : At the initial stage, loss of moisture from the ricinoleic acid glyceride causes a decrease in acetyl value but subsequently there is a formation of hydroxy acids from olein and linolein (present to the extent of about 10% in castor oil). These

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

two phenomena counteract each other in such a manner that the fall in acetyl value is less than what would be expected from the rise in iodine value. After a while, however, the curve becomes regular which supports the view expressed regarding the course of chemical action taking place during the heating *i.e.* the hydroxy acid formed gives up a molecule of water and molecules with conjugated double bonds are finally produced by rearrangement.

The development of conjugated system in accordance with the theoretical assumption is thus verified.

The extent of polymerisation of the oil molecules will be manifested from Table III which shows increased values for specific gravity, viscosity and molecular weight of the oil samples after heat treatment.

TABLE III

Temp.	Time of heating (hrs.)	Sp. gr.	Red-wood (seconds)	Viscosity (poise)	Mol. wt.		Average value Mol. wt.
					I	II	
50°	Original	0.9572	1812	3.41	854	857	856
	1	.9573	—	—	864	866	865
	2	.9576	1336	3.47	912	916	914
	3	.9581	1350	3.77	995	997	996
	4	.9590	1585	4.12	1047	1050	1049
75°	1	0.9585	1490	3.97	918	920	919
	2	.95968	1592	4.14	1046	1050	1048
	3	.9604	1608	4.18	1136	1139	1138
	4	.9609	1652	4.27	1235	1240	1235
100°	1	0.96092	1658	4.30	1250	1252	1251
	2	.9616	1742	4.53	1395	1392	1348
	3	.9620	1884	4.89	1602	1600	1601
	4	.9629	2105	5.47	1840	1845	1843

The relation between the molecular weight and Diene value is shown in Fig. 3. Since the increase in molecular weight is not in simple multiples of the original oil, it can be

concluded that the polymerisation of the glycerides does not take place regularly and by a simple doubling of molecules as in ordinary polymerisation reactions in organic chemistry but that the glycerides are first decomposed into fatty acids and lower glycerides and the liberated fatty acid molecules then undergo polymerisation. This, however, requires substantiation by further experimental evidence. Determination of the acid value might throw some light on this point.

FIG. 3

The results obtained reveal that by gradual heating there is a considerable increase in unsaturation in the molecule and also a corresponding regular increase of molecular weight. Whilst progressive polymerisation is evidenced by the gradual increase in molecular weight, similar changes in iodine value and Diene value indicate simultaneous development of conjugated system in the molecule. With prolonged heating at higher temperatures it is to be expected therefore, that the polymerisation will be extensively marked and would result in the ultimate formation of a highly viscous rubber-like mass when the Diene value will abruptly fall. Further experiments are being conducted to illustrate these points.

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